

EVALUATION OF THYROID FUNCTION AMONG POST-MENOPAUSAL WOMEN IN MOSUL CITY

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Abstract: Background: This study investigates age-related changes in thyroid function among post-menopausal women. Thyroid dysfunction, particularly elevated thyroid-stimulating hormone (TSH) and altered levels of Free T3 and Free T4, often increases with age. Post-menopausal women are particularly susceptible to these shifts due to hormonal and metabolic changes, making thyroid health monitoring critical in this population.

Methods: A cross-sectional, retrospective analysis was conducted on 100 post-menopausal women aged 51-60 years. Participants were selected based on specific inclusion and exclusion criteria, including the absence of known thyroid dysfunction, diabetes, hypertension, chronic kidney disease, or malignancies. The function of the thyroid gland was assessed by measuring TSH, Free T3, and Free T4 levels, with statistical analyses including Spearman's correlation to evaluate age-related changes.

Results: The study shows an increase in TSH levels in post-menopausal women, with a concurrent decrease in both Free T3 and Free T4 as age progresses. A significant positive correlation was found between age and TSH levels ($r = 0.382$, $p < 0.01$). Additionally, significant negative correlations were observed between age and both Free T3 ($r = -0.235$, $p < 0.05$) and Free T4 ($r = -0.699$, $p < 0.01$).

Conclusion: The study findings indicate that as women age in the post-menopausal stage, there is a significant increase in TSH levels and a decline in free T3 and free T4 levels. These hormonal changes can impact metabolic, cardiovascular, and bone health. Therefore routine thyroid function monitoring is recommended to facilitate early detection and prompt treatment of potential thyroid dysfunction.

Keywords: Post-menopausal women, Thyroid dysfunction, TSH levels, Free T3 and Free T4 variations, Mosul city.

Introduction:

Endocrine glands go through alterations as individuals' age. A decrease in the availability of TSH, a diminished capability of the thyroid gland to respond to TSH might lead to an increase in TSH secretion despite the lack of apparent thyroid pathology in addition to a decrease in circulating T4 levels. Subclinical hypothyroidism, characterized by normal Free T4 levels and elevated TSH levels, is frequently observed in the older population. Furthermore gender-specific differences in TSH and Free T4 levels have been noted, with older women showing increased TSH levels but no changes in Free T4 levels.^{1, 2, 3}

The thyroid hormone governs the metabolic processes of the body, which includes the regulation of reproductive activities.⁴

Thyroid disorders primarily impact females. Thyroid illnesses are more prevalent in women than men, with a five to 20-fold difference in occurrence. Research has demonstrated a positive correlation between age and the prevalence of thyroid disease. Autoimmunity of the thyroid gland, hypothyroidism, nodular goitre, and cancer exhibit higher prevalence in post-menopausal and older women relative to younger women.⁵

Common signs of hypothyroidism, such as cognitive impairment, reduced mental processing speed, fatigue, and muscle spasms, can sometimes be misinterpreted as symptoms of menopause. Research has shown that thyroid hormones have a similar impact on brain function as estrogen. They influence cellular metabolism, gene expression, intercellular signaling, and the production of enzymes essential for neurotransmitter synthesis.⁶

Based on morphological investigations, flattening of the thyroid epithelium is seen due to degenerative changes. Additionally, the thyroid follicles decrease in size, while there is a rise in the growth of both connective tissue of the fibrous type and lymphoid tissue. Consequently, the thyroid gland may progressively diminish in size. In individuals over the age of 80, the thyroid gland's ability to take in iodine diminishes, it is 40% lower compared to those who are 30 years old.⁷

Estrogens primarily function to raise the levels of thyroxine binding globulin (TBG) in the bloodstream. TBG is a protein produced by the liver, and estrogens strengthen the oligosaccharide chains of TBG, namely the N-acetylglucosamine type, which in turn decreases its removal from the body.⁸

The serum TBG levels undergo significant fluctuations in the period leading up to and following menopause. This occurrence is associated with elevated levels of TBG that occur with aging, compensating for the decline in estrogen levels.⁸

Menopause, refers to the permanent cessation of menstrual periods and the loss of fertility in most women. The onset of menopause often takes place between the ages of 45 and 55. Menopause is the absence of vaginal bleeding for a continuous period of one year.⁹ it is advisable to regularly check menopausal women for thyroid illness. Since the symptoms of thyroid illness might imitate those of menopause.¹⁰

Aim of the study:

The purpose of this study is to assess the thyroid profile of postmenopausal women and to identify any correlations between age and thyroid profile due to the scarcity of local literature on this topic.

Material and methods:

The objectives of the study were explained to the patients, and an informed verbal consent was obtained. The study was also approved by institutional ethical committee. Participants were selected based on specific inclusion and exclusion criteria. Key historical information, including symptoms and signs observed during physical examination, in addition to the patient's medical history and medications were documented.

Type of the study: This study employed a cross-sectional retrospective design to assess thyroid profiles in 100 post-menopausal women.

Inclusion Criteria: Participants were included in the study if they met the following criteria: Postmenopausal women aged 51-60 years. Any female within the specified age range who had not had menstruation for a minimum duration of 1 year was considered as postmenopausal.¹¹

Exclusion Criteria: Individuals were excluded from the study based on the following criteria: a known case of thyroid disorder, hypertension, diabetes mellitus, chronic kidney diseases, or a patient with diagnosed ovarian and uterine cancers, Individuals receiving medications such as iodide, amiodarone, propranolol, lithium, glucocorticoids, somatostatins and salicylates, Individuals undergoing hormone replacement therapy and those who had a previous hysterectomy.⁸

Sample collection and analysis: Blood samples (5 ml) were collected under aseptic conditions. Serum was separated by centrifugation (3000 rpm for 15 minutes) and analyzed for TSH, Free T3 and Free T4 levels using a mini vidas hormone analyzer, which operates based on immunoassay principles, specifically immunofluorescence.

Statistical analysis: The analysis of statistical data was conducted utilizing SPSS software Ver. 25. A normality test was conducted to assess distribution of the data, which indicated a non-normal distribution. Consequently, a non-parametric parametric analysis was applied. Spearman's correlation method was used to calculate the correlation between thyroid profile and age.

Results:

This study analyzed the relationship between age and thyroid function markers (TSH, Free T3, Free T4) in a post-menopausal sample to assess age-related changes in thyroid health. A normality test was conducted specifically Shapiro-Wilk test, which revealed that Free T3, Free T4, and age were not normally distributed ($p < 0.05$). As a result, non-parametric analysis was employed to assess that data, as shown in Table 1.

Table1: Shapiro-Wilk Test (A normality test).

Tests of Normality			
	Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	df	Sig.
Free T3 (pg/mL)	.936	100	0.000
Free T4 (ng/dL)	.819	100	0.000
TSH Level (mIU/L)	.978	100	0.095
Age	.948	100	0.001

Table2: The Descriptive Statistics.

Descriptive Statistics			
	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Age (Year)	100	54.80	2.574
TSH Level (mIU/L)	100	5.231	1.5902
Free T3 (pg/ml)	100	1.2686	.54632
Free T4 (ng/dl)	100	.5321	.31136

The mean age of participants was 54.80 years (SD = 2.574), with a mean TSH level of 5.231 mIU/L (SD = 1.5902), Free T3 of 1.2686 pg/mL (SD = 0.54632), and Free T4 of 0.5321 ng/dL (SD = 0.31136) as shown in Table 2.

Table3: Correlations of the parameters.

Spearman's rho Correlations				
		TSH Level (mIU/L)	Free T3 (pg/ml)	Free T4 (ng/dl)
Post-menopausal Age (Year)	Correlation Coefficient	0.382**	-0.235*	-0.699**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.019	.000
**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).				
*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).				

Spearman's correlation analysis revealed a considerable positive association between age and TSH levels ($r = 0.382$, $p < 0.01$), as well as significant negative correlations between age and Free T3 ($r = -0.235$, $p < 0.05$) and Free T4 ($r = -0.699$, $p < 0.01$). These correlations are shown in Table 3 and are visually represented in Figures 1–3.

Figure1: The Correlation between Post-menopausal Age (Year) & TSH (mIU/L): The graph illustrates a positive slope, indicating that as women age in their post-menopausal phase, their TSH levels tend to increase.

Figure2: The Correlation between Post-menopausal Age (Year) & Free T3: The chart has a negative slope, indicating a weak but significant inverse relationship ($r = -0.235$, $p < 0.05$). As age increases, Free T3 levels tend to decrease.

Figure3: The Correlation between Post-menopausal Age (Year) & Free T4: The graph demonstrate a steep negative slope, indicating a significant inverse relationship ($r = -0.699$, $p < 0.01$). Free T4 levels decrease significantly as age increases.

Discussion:

This study aimed to investigate the relationship between age and thyroid function markers (TSH, Free T3, and Free T4) in postmenopausal women. The results revealed an increase in TSH levels in postmenopausal women, with a concurrent decrease in both Free T3 and Free T4 as age progresses. A significant positive correlation between age and TSH levels ($r = 0.382$, $p < 0.01$). And a strong inverse relationship between age and both Free T3 ($r = -0.235$, $p < 0.05$) and Free T4 levels ($r = -0.699$, $p < 0.01$). These findings reflect well-established physiological changes in thyroid function associated with menopausal transitions and aging.

The observed increase in TSH levels with advancing age is consistent with existing literature suggesting a compensatory response to declining thyroid hormone levels. Aging is associated with reduced thyroid production efficiency, prompting the pituitary gland to secrete more TSH to maintain hormonal balance. This mechanism is particularly pronounced in postmenopausal women, where hormonal and metabolic shifts, such as declining estrogen levels, further modulate thyroid function. The inverse relationship between age and Free T3 and Free T4 levels likely reflects diminished thyroid gland output and reduced peripheral conversion of T4 to the more active T3, as reported in previous studies (e.g., Hollowell et al., 2002; Rojas et al., 2007).^{12,13}

Several factors contribute to these age-related thyroid changes in postmenopausal women. First, the aging thyroid gland undergoes structural and functional decline, leading to reduced hormone production. The pituitary gland compensates by increasing TSH secretion (Bremner et al., 2012).¹⁴ Second, the sharp reduction in estrogen following menopause impacts thyroid function and hormone bioavailability, further stimulating TSH production as the body adapts to hormonal imbalances (Del Ghianda et al., 2013).⁸ Third, aging slows the enzymatic conversion of T4 to T3, exacerbating declines in Free T3 levels and triggering

compensatory TSH elevations (Goodman et al., 2023).¹⁰ Finally, the increased prevalence of thyroid autoimmunity with age may impair hormone production and amplify TSH levels (Bordoloi et al., 2018).¹⁵

The interplay of these factors highlights the complexity of thyroid regulation in postmenopausal women, highlighting the importance of thyroid health monitoring in this age group. These findings align with prior research documenting age-related changes in thyroid markers. For instance, Hollowell et al. (2002), in their NHANES study, observed elevated TSH levels in older women, corroborating the present results¹². Similarly, Rojas et al. (2007) and Pearce et al. (2008) reported significant increases in TSH among postmenopausal women^{13,16}. Bordoloi et al. (2018) and Patwa et al. (2016) also found higher TSH levels in postmenopausal women compared to their premenopausal counterparts, emphasizing the impact of menopause on thyroid physiology^{15,17}. Interestingly, Bremner et al. (2012) suggested that age-related TSH increases might reflect changes in the TSH regulatory set point or reduced TSH bioactivity, pointing to alterations in thyroid hormone regulation rather than direct thyroid dysfunction.¹⁴

Conclusion:

This study highlights significant association between age and thyroid function markers in post-menopausal women. Age-related changes observed in thyroid function driven by hormonal imbalances such as the decline in estrogen levels and the reduced peripheral conversion of T4 to T3, may lead to alteration in thyroid hormone levels. Early detection and monitoring of thyroid markers, particularly TSH, is crucial in this population to improve health outcomes.

Recommendations:

Future longitudinal studies could provide insight into the progression of thyroid changes with aging. Additionally, investigating lifestyle or genetic factors could enhance understanding of individual variability in age-related thyroid function.

Limitations:

One limitation of this study is its cross-sectional design, which restricts the capacity to establish a causal relationship between thyroid function changes and age.

Conflict of interest:

No conflicts of interests were declared by the authors.

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